

ASSIGNMENT
ON
READER'S GUIDE TO PERIODICAL
LITERATURE

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Reader's Guide to Periodical Literature

AUTHORITY

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INTRODUCTION

The Reader's Guide to Periodical Literature is a reference guide to recently published articles in periodical magazines and scholarly journals. The reader's guide has been published regularly since **1901** by **The H.W Wilson Company**, and is a staple of public and academic references libraries throughout the United States and Canada.

The company merged with EBSCO publishing in June 2011. The Reader's guide to periodicals literature is now published by Grey House Publishing. It is a database containing comprehensive indexing of the most popular general interest periodicals published in the United States.

The retrospective index of general periodicals published from 1890 to 1982 is also available. Originally, The Reader's Guide was published on

a biweekly basis, with later issues incorporating the previous content in larger copies until the index for the entire year was published.

SCOPE

Unabridged edition

- The main purpose of the Reader's Guide to periodical literature is to provide comprehensive coverage of popular and important periodicals and providing trusted, broad information for **Educators, Students** and **Library patrons** seeking detailed current events coverage, curriculum support or access to quality periodicals.
- This database delivers comprehensive indexing of around 300 of the most popular and important periodicals published in United States and Canada, thereby indexing articles about topic of current and historical interest.
- Readers Guide to Periodical Literature should be used to search for periodical containing information in a particular topic or to find publication of interest.
- Access to over three million articles from approximately 375 leading magazines; many are peer reviewed.
- It offers high school and college students, teachers, public library patrons and researchers of all kinds an easy-to-use index to a broad range of general interest popular magazines.
- Among the hundreds of subject covered are Aeronautics, Aging, Astronomy, Automobiles, Biography, Business, Children, Computers, Consumer Education, Religion, Sports, Health, History, Current Events, Hobbies, Home, Journalism, Medicine, Science, Photography, Food, Education, Nutrition, News, Environment, Music, Politics, Fashion, Film, Fine Arts and Television.

- Three paperback are delivered March to September and include 800 pages each. The cumulative library-bound annual, published each year in January, includes over 2,500 pages covering over 160,000 articles.

Abridged Edition

- The Abridged Reader's Guide to Periodical Literature provides a smaller, more affordable subset of Reader's Guide to periodical Literature. It delivers comprehensive indexing of 72 of the most popular general – interest periodicals published in the United States and Canada.
- This edition features complete indexing of the most popular magazines in libraries today, as well as subscription information for each magazine indexed.
- Two paperback are delivered March to September and include 500 pages each. The cumulative Library-bound annual, published each year in January, includes 1,000 pages

TREATMENT

- Entries contain the following and follow a definite arrangement

Subject heading

Title of Article

Author of article

Name of magazine or journals

Volume Number

Page number

Date of publication.

ARRANGEMENT

- Author and subject are arranged in one alphabet. Under author and subjects, titles are arranged also in alphabetical order by the first word, initial articles being disregarded. Under personal names titles by author precede those about him. Subdivisions of a subject are arranged alphabetically under the subject. Geographical subheads follow the other subdivisions in a separate alphabet.

Format

Reader's Guide is available in both print and online.

Print Format

- It is hard cover binding.
- Easy to read.
- Entries are divided in two columns.
- The quality of paper is good.

Online features

- Reader's guides to periodical literature is updated daily.

- Access to information is flexible and easy in the Reader's Guide. The following search methods are available :-

1. **Subject Access**– The plain language terminology used in the subject headings insures users will find the information they need.

2. **Author access** – Both subject and author entries are given in one alphabet and both provide all the information necessary to locate an article.

3. **Cross reference**– literally thousands of cross reference help users expand the scope of their searches.

SPECIAL FEATURE

- Unique name and subject authority files which guarantee names and subject headings are consistent wherever they appear.
- Title enhancement : to clarify the content of articles with ambiguous titles
- Complete subscription information for each magazine indexed.
- A separate index of book review which have appeared in the covered magazine.

CONCLUSION:

Reader's Guide to periodical Literature indexes articles found in a variety of periodicals and is the best place to search indexed entries of an author and subject. This database provides important, extensive

information for educators, students and archives users looking for all embracing modern events coverage, curriculum support or access to quality journals.

REFERENCES:

www.hwwilsoninprint.com

www.ebscohost.com